

The Digital Transformation of the FMCG Industry: A Glimpse

Hetal Kherala
Assistant Professor (Commerce)
R.C. College of Commerce
hetal.kherala@gmail.com

Abstract

India is transforming digitally, as it affects other industries then how the FMCG business in India is left behind. Here, we can say this is a midst of a digital revolution. As per the estimation of 40% of FMCG purchase in some select categories will be on-line and as a FMCG distribution channel through E-commerce will grow by US \$6 Bn. During the festive seasons on-line shopping spirit is at an all-time high among the brand crazy consumers and different brands are launching new products in the market offline as well as online. Last year in the month of October and November, online retailers in the country sold goods worth US \$ 4.3 billion approx. 29,947 crore and during the same period Indian shoppers spent a Rs. 15,300 crore (US \$ billion) during discount events hosted by e-commerce giant Amazon, Flipkart, Paytm Mall and others. In the present paper the researcher has tried to find out how many internet users are doing online purchasing which leads to a digital transformation of the FMCG industry, amount spent on digital advertisement.

Key words: OOH (Out-of-Home), ADEX (Award for Design Excellent product design)

“Digital Marketers need to make the business case to convince those who control the budgets that we require to implement our digital plans. Otherwise change won’t be fast enough and the effectiveness of our marketing activity is likely to decline as consumers or business customers switch to new platforms; we risk ‘missing the boat’”. Mike Berry (Berry and Chaffey, 2012)

Introduction:

When the applications of the Internet for marketing were first explored in the 1990s, some advocates urged adoption of Internet marketing since it was ‘quick, cheap and easy’. May be this was true at the time, in a relative sense; it was possible to get an edge over slower moving competitor. Today, few would argue that e-marketing is ‘quick, cheap and easy’ since the popularity of digital technologies with consumers and business has made it such medium which is highly competitive. Digital technology has changed both the business and operating models and many leaders need to revise their understanding whilst trying to run a business in change, often in a market that is transforming much faster than their business.

To be involved in e-marketing is certainly increasing since there are constant changes in features and functionality from all the major platforms such as Face book, Google+ and Twitter. New platforms are rapidly adopted like; Foursquare, Instagram and Pin interest, new e commerce websites like amazon. in, snap deal, flip kart, lime road, e-bay, alibaba.com etc. have all become popular since that emergence of the internet networks. The growth of mobile internet usage through smart phones and tablets has further changes our options for marketing.

In a broader way there are two ways of thinking about the impact of digital on business. First, in terms of how it manifests itself, and second in terms of competitive opportunity. The following figure sets out a hierarchical model of digital business that defines the activity in one of three groups.

Source: Good Growth Ltd. 2014.

This part is dominated by professional service and some digital services businesses who can manipulate billions of data points on behalf of very large organizations such banks, retailers and governments.

- Digital as Disruptive innovation: This part is dominated to entrepreneurial part where new products and services come into being that either impossible or commercially unviable in the pre- digital age. Whilst this is where fortunes can be made for the founders and early investors, over time this business will establish and sustain themselves through the tools and techniques required to manage a digital route to market.
- Digital as a route to market: This part is dominated to transformation of existing products and services or allowing the development of new products and services within established markets.

There are two most crucial point for FMCG industry;

1) Digital Influence

2) E- Commerce

- Digital influence means use of the internet during the purchase journey i.e. Pre Purchase, Purchase and Post Purchase.
- E-Commerce defines the use of the internet for the actual purchasing activity.

It is difficult to find a person who have never buy single product online. Many of us are buying our daily groceries online. There are different modes of digitalization are;

- Social Media
- Digital Branding
- Company Websites
- Blogging
- Online PR (public relation) and Blogger
- SEO (Search Engine Optimization)
- Email Marketing
- Affiliate Marketing
- Digital Advertising
- Video Marketing

Present E-Commerce industry in India: As we all know India is a developing in all the terms then how left behind in E-Commerce. India is the fastest growing market with 525 Mn digitally influenced users at present in the E-Commerce sector. Revenue generated from the sector is expected to increase from US\$ 39 Bn in 2017 to US \$ 120 billion in 2020, growing at an annual rate of 51%, the highest in the world and E-Commerce industry in India witnessed 21 private equity and venture capital deals worth US \$ 2.1 Bn in 2017 and 40 deals worth US \$ 1.129 million in the first half of 2018, as per the report of IBEF updated last year 2018.

Internet Users in India

Figure: 1 Numbers of internet users in millions

Source: www.statista.com

The figure showing the data of numbers of internet users in million. Due to increasing use of internet users had tank up the FMCG sector's online sales.

As per the report of the consulting firm The Boston Consulting Group and Google titled “Decoding Digital Impact: A \$45 Billion Opportunity in FMCG”, estimated that by 2020, 40% of all fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) purchases in India will go online and will make a business of \$5-6 billion business.

Presently consumers are purchasing any product by comparing it with different e-commerce website. They look for things to buy online and majority of brands are advertised on-line, sales in certain fast moving consumer goods are expected to be high i.e., “digitally influenced”. The most

preferred items for online shopping are baby care, fragrances, over 50% of sales are expected to be influenced by online marketing, 45% are in apparel, and 60% are in consumer electronics but for routine need products like laundry and toiletries the sales are expected to come less than 25% through online or digital advertising.

The big FMCG firms in India disbursed only about 10% of their advertising budgets on digital advertising, according to the report which can rise up to 25-30% and be worth \$1.1 billion by 2020 and even it may reach 50-70% for select/selected premium brands, the report said. Here the researcher has tried to find out the exact expenditure done by different FMCG companies on digital marketing and probable ROI but no data has been found. The following chart represent the amount spends on advertising it includes Indian Media.

Figure 1 Growth of Advertising Market

Source: Pitch Medison Advertising Report 2019

As per the report of Pitch Medison Advertising report 2019, it is predicted that the advertising market will grow 16.4 % during present financial year. It is also stated in the report that “the Indian media & advertising industry is on a high growth path, and appears to be finally reaping the benefits of demonetization and the Goods & Services Tax (GST), that had hit the growth of Adex in 2016-17, highlighting last year’s achievement, the advertising industry grew by 14.6% in 2018; surpassing their estimate of 12.03%”. They also said that FMCG automobiles, retail and e-commerce were the largest contributors to the ADEX, digital advertising to grow 33%, Cinema advertising b 30%, and radio by 12 % and outdoor by 11%.

There is a change in the searching of product in this digitally influenced market. Consumers are searching for the “problem solution” space instead of conventional usage space; for example,

searches for problems like hair fall are significantly higher than the category 'Shampoo' or 'stain remover' rather than 'Vanish' or other related products, it is reported in the BCG report that, this type of searches is 7times higher.

This is important to note, that brands of FMCG industry need to invest in different category depending upon the penetration of the products. E.g., there is a higher share of consumption in perfumes and baby care is digitally influenced, whilst in other, such as Laundry and other toilet care it is less than 25% of the consumption digitally influenced.

Conclusion:

“Mera desh badal raha he” when the 50% of all e-commerce sales in India done through Smartphone's, when people have a wider range of FMCG products available online, then it is a tuff period for offline retailers. Digital transformation is accepted but at the same time how we could neglect the small traders and retailers who are struggling to sell their products. IN the race of Brands and online business they could not be omitted that's why Ministry of Commerce had framed a new e-commerce policy which could provide oxygen to the dry retail market.

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